

Deliverable D6.1

Report on all Open Call activities

Project Title	Artificial Intelligence For Image Data Analysis In The Life Sciences
Project Acronym	AI4Life
Project Number	101057970
Project Start Date	01.09.2022
Project Duration	36 Months

WP N° & Title	WP6: Open Calls and Challenges
WP Leaders	HT
Deliverable Lead Beneficiary	HT
Dissemination Level	PU
Contractual Delivery Date	31.08.2025 (M36)
Actual Delivery Date	10.09.2025
Authors	Mehdi Seifi, Florian Jug, Vera Galinova, Beatriz Serrano-Solano, Joran Deschamps
Reviewers	Arrate Muñoz-Barrutia

AI4Life has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement number 101057970. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Change Log

Version	Date	Author	Description of changes
v0.1	01.08.2025	Mehdi Seifi (HT), Florian Jug (HT), Vera Galinova (HT), Beatriz Serrano-Solano (EMBL-Bio-Hub)	Initial draft
v0.2	11.08.2025	Joran Deschamps (HT)	Suggestions and edits
v0.3	19.08.2025	Florian Jug (HT)	Draft submitted for consortium review
v0.4	05.09.2025	Vera Galinova (HT)	Consortium feedback incorporated
v1.0	10.09.2025	Vera Galinova (HT), Beatriz Serrano-Solano (EMBL-Bio-Hub), Mehdi Seifi (HT), Joran Deschamps (HT)	Final edits

Acronyms and Abbreviations

AI	Artificial Intelligence
BMZ	BioImage Model Zoo
CKD	Chronic Kidney Disease
CLEM	Correlative Light and Electron Microscopy
COCO	Common Objects in Context (dataset/format)
CSV	Comma-Separated Values
D	Deliverable
ECM	Extracellular Matrix
EMPIAR	Electron Microscopy Public Image Archive
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud

FCS	Flow Cytometry Standard
FDR	Fisher Discriminant Ratio
FIB–SEM	Focused Ion Beam–Scanning Electron Microscopy
IDR	Image Data Resource
iPSC	Induced Pluripotent Stem Cells
KIF	Kinesin Family (proteins)
MND	Motor Neuron Disease
N2V	Noise2Void
OC	Open Call
QC	Quality Control
SAM	Segment Anything Model
v	Version
WP	Work Package

Table of contents

Acronyms and Abbreviations	2
Executive Summary	4
1. Introduction	5
2. Description of work	5
2.1. Project Calls and Selection Procedure	6
2.1.1 OC1: initial procedure and first selection	7
2.1.2 OC2: updates to the selection procedure and second selection	8
2.1.3 OC3: fine-tuned selection procedure and last selection	10
2.2. Results of Selected Open Call Projects	10
2.2.1 Projects of OC1	10
2.2.2 Projects of OC2	14
2.2.3 Projects of OC3	17
3. Conclusion	21

Executive Summary

This deliverable reports on AI4Life's Open Call activities within WP6: Open Calls and Challenges throughout the project.

The AI4Life Open Calls were created to provide life scientists facing unmet image-analysis needs with practical AI workflows, prioritising problems of broad relevance and potential reusability across research groups and domains.

Over three iterations (OC1, OC2, and OC3), the process of application and selection of AI image analysis projects was refined to balance user participation and feasibility:

1. Scale and outcomes: OC1 received 72 submissions (62 of them eligible) and selected 8 projects. OC2 received 51 and selected 7. OC3 received 28 and selected 7. Leading to 22 supported projects in total.
2. Application process: applicants were asked to provide representative data and a brief project summary, enabling reviewers to assess data quality, availability of ground truth, and suitability for deep learning.
3. Approach to assessment: Reviewers had access to anonymised application information and used a set of criteria (quality, effort, excitement) which were then combined into a final score used to rank projects. From OC2 forward, a consultation phase helped verify readiness, identify cases solvable with existing tools, and offer feedback to non-selected projects.

Supported projects covered a range of imaging modalities and tasks, including denoising, segmentation, tracking, and quantitative analysis. The teams produced reproducible workflows, trained models, and documentation aligned with FAIR and EOSC-ready practices. Outcomes and data have been shared via the BioImage Archive, EMPIAR, the BioImage Model Zoo, GitHub, and Zenodo.

The Open Calls contributed directly to the objectives of AI4Life by improving access to AI methods, setting expectations for data and model sharing, supporting developer-facing services, integrating models into common analysis platforms, and providing targeted guidance through consultations. Early publications have resulted, and additional manuscripts are in preparation.

Overall, this deliverable documents our approach to matching community needs with AI-based image analysis solutions. The Open Call process described here offers a basis for similar initiatives.

1. Introduction

The AI4Life project is part of the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme, led by the project coordinator Euro-BioImaging and in which 10 partners participated, 5 of them being European Research Infrastructures. The project started in September 2022 and ends in August 2025.

AI4Life aims to bring state-of-the-art AI-based image analysis to life scientists by establishing and supporting innovative services targeting researchers in the life sciences and computational methods developers in AI and computer vision.

More specifically, the objectives of AI4Life are

- **Objective 1: Democratised availability of AI-based image analysis methods** as a FAIR service accessible through the AI4Life service landscape and computationally powered by the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) infrastructure.
- **Objective 2: Establish standards** for the submission, storage, and FAIR access of reference data, reference annotations (ground-truth), trained AI models, and trainable AI methods.
- **Objective 3: Simple model deployment, sharing, and dissemination** of AI-based methods as a new developer-facing service of the [BioImage Model Zoo \(BMZ\)](#).
- **Objective 4: Organise Open Calls and Challenges** for outstanding image analysis.
- **Objective 5: Empower common image analysis platforms with AI tools.**
- **Objective 6: Organise outreach and training events.**

This deliverable is part of WP6, *Open Calls and Challenges*. WP6 contributes to Objectives 4 and 6 by organising Open Calls and raising awareness of AI4Life and the opportunities it offers to life scientists.

2. Description of work

The AI4Life Open Calls (OCs) are meant to provide life scientists who have unmet image analysis needs with adequate deep learning workflows for their desired analyses. We were particularly interested in problems that are likely not unique to a specific applicant, but instead limit the rate of scientific discovery for multiple individuals and/or scientific groups and communities.

The OCs provided technical support to researchers, scientists, and the wider bioimage analysis community. Life Scientists who submitted specific analysis issues and needs related to their work were screened and evaluated by international experts, and a subset of selected projects received full project support.

Below, we will first describe the selection procedure of our first OC, and detail the projects we have received, the demographics of the applicants, and how we selected the projects that received our support. Subsequently, we describe for OC2 and OC3 how and why we improved the selection process based on our collected experiences, and again summarise received applications, demographics, and selection outcomes.

After that, we introduce, grouped by OC, the purpose of the selected projects and the work we conducted to help the applicants achieve their goals.

2.1. Project Calls and Selection Procedure

After running three OCs, we have optimised our selection procedure and analysis support workflow, which is summarized in the figure below.

Next, we will describe the selection procedure we implemented for each OC and our motivation and actions to improve them over time.

2.1.1 OC1: initial procedure and first selection

Applicants applied by providing information about their data, scientific questions, current workflows, and the challenges they face in analysing them. In total, we received **72 applications** for image analysis support. We first conducted an eligibility check (performed by Damian Dalle Nogare, Image Analysis Facility, Human Technopole, and Florian Jug, AI4Life). This check was syntactic by nature, addressing questions such as: "Is the submitted project sufficiently detailed?", "Does the information provided tell a coherent story fit for external review?". At this stage, only 10 projects were excluded, leaving 62 eligible in total. We intended only to filter projects that drew an incomplete picture or were missing important information, and leave the judgment of the scientific aspects entirely to our reviewers.

In parallel to the application process, we opened a call for volunteer reviewers. We have received 17 self-nominations, of which we nominated 8 reviewers to help us with the reviewing work. We supplemented those 8 reviewers with 8 reviewers from within AI4Life, giving us a total of 16 reviewers to evaluate the project proposals (applications) we received independently.

Each of the **62 eligible projects** was then reviewed by at least 3 independent reviewers, who were instructed to evaluate their randomly assigned projects using a pre-defined form that helped them to consistently answer the following questions:

- Is the proposed project amenable to Deep Learning methods/approaches/tools?
- Does the project have well-defined goals (and are those goals the correct ones)?
- Will a complete solution to the proposed project require additional classical analysis routines to be developed?
- Will the project, once completed, be useful for a broader scientific user base?
- Will the project require the generation of significant amounts of (reusable) training data?
- Will the project likely boil down to finding and using the right (existing) tool?
- Will approaches/scripts/models developed to solve this project likely be reusable for other, similar projects?
- Will the project, once completed, be interesting to computational researchers (e.g., within a public challenge)?
- Might the applicant(s) have a 'problematic attitude' towards publicly sharing (parts) of their data once the project is completed?
- Does the available data suggest that the proposed project is feasible (results good enough to make users happy)?
- Is it to be expected that we can (within reasonable effort) improve on a pre-existing analysis pipeline?

Additionally, the reviewers were tasked with identifying parts of the project that might be improved, evaluating whether deep learning can be of help, and providing an estimation of the time needed to support the project. Additional details can be found on the [AI4Life Website](#).

After we received all reviews, a group of 6 members of AI4Life compiled application scores according to reviewer verdicts. To this end, we first aggregated all reviews per project by averaging numerical values and concatenating textual evaluations. We then developed three project scores: a *quality* score (main metric), a total *effort* score, and a slightly more subjective *excitement* score.

The *quality score* was computed by taking a weighted average of the evaluations we received in the review form (see [AI4Life Website](#)). The score obtained from some questions needed to be inverted in order to obtain “high-is-better” grading, before applying the weighted average.

The *effort score* was taking the (minimum) time estimates for label data generation, successfully completing the project, and the resulting value corresponding to the estimated total person-month to completion.

The *excitement score* is simply the average of the values received as answers to question 8 (Will the project, once completed, be interesting to computational researchers (e.g., within a public challenge)?).

The **final score** is defined by:

$$s = 0.75 * (\text{quality/effort}) + 0.25 * \text{excitement_score}$$

At a similar *quality* and *excitement*, this formula favours projects that are estimated to necessitate shorter time to completion, which aligns with our aim to help more individuals through the AI4Life Open Calls.

Ranked by final score (in [Section 2.2.1](#)) and selected up to capacity, we ended up with a total of **8 selected projects**.

2.1.2 OC2: updates to the selection procedure and second selection

Following the first Open Call, it became evident that a number of highly-ranked applications could not be classified as deep learning-ready projects, either because of a lack of available ground-truth or adequacy of existing non-deep learning tools. While such proposals could still benefit from short-term support by image analysis experts, for instance, to help the researchers understand how to acquire the necessary ground-truth data, they did not fit our target audience of challenging deep learning compatible problems. Furthermore, some selected projects encountered delays of a month or more owing to the lack of readiness of the data, ranging from the absence of ground-truth

data of sufficient quality to the necessity to re-acquire data in a different way. We therefore decided to improve the OC process both on the application and selection sides.

To help reviewers better assess the readiness and deep-learning applicability of each project, we modified the application form to include two key types of files:

- Relevant and representative data (images and annotations, where applicable)
- A four-slide presentation of the project following a specific template

The data enabled reviewers to accurately evaluate image quality and/or the ground-truth, as well as the appropriateness and feasibility of the requested analysis. The structured presentation, in turn, helped reviewers quickly grasp the essential information (project aim, data, and current workflow).

In the second Open Call, we received **51 applications in total**, all of which passed the eligibility check, a process similar to the one performed in OC1.

To improve our selection process and better serve the community, we introduced a **consultation phase** after the eligibility check for the second Open Call. This phase had two purposes: first, to gain a deeper understanding of highly ranked projects and ensure they presented challenges not already addressed by existing tools, and second, to provide constructive feedback to projects that would ultimately not be selected. To identify candidates for this phase, we added a new review question: "Can the project be solved in one or two consultation sessions?"

Together with the reusability question (see OC1), this new question was combined into a *consultation* score. Applicants selected for consultation were chosen based on two criteria: a threshold on this *consultation* score and another on a *project* score similar to that used in OC1.

We invited **20 applicants** selected for consultation to book a one-hour slot within a predefined two-week schedule for an online meeting to discuss their image analysis problem. During the meeting, they presented their image data and the challenge they faced, while a panel of experts provided feedback on their current pipeline and guidance. The feedback covered all aspects of their projects, from data and ground-truth acquisition, image analysis pipelines, potential improvements using existing tools, and opinions on the feasibility of their project. A second consultation was offered to applicants for whom a solution seemed attainable in an additional image analysis support session or when concerns remained about the feasibility of the project or the availability of relevant data and ground-truth.

The consultation phase panels were composed of members of the AI4Life partners institutes and of the Image Analysis Facility at Human Technopole (Italy). We ensured

that typically three or four experts were present for each session. After each meeting, the experts' comments were consolidated for the final project selection phase. Final selection was performed by all experts based on scores and consultation results.

Ultimately, **7 projects** were selected for support by AI4Life experts.

2.1.3 OC3: fine-tuned selection procedure and last selection

For the third Open Call, we kept the same application form and received **28 applications** in total, all of which passed the eligibility check. We simplified the review scoring system by asking reviewers to directly provide an estimate of the following scores (0–5):

- Readiness of the project
- Applicability of deep learning to the problem
- Excitement about the project

13 applications were pre-selected for further evaluation based on thresholds to the aggregated (with equal weight) scores. A consultation phase, following the same format as in OC2, was conducted, with only **10 consultation** sessions due to applicants being unavailable to participate.

Finally, **7 projects** were selected for support in OC3 using the same final selection process as in OC2.

2.2. Results of Selected Open Call Projects

Throughout each project support, the AI4Life experts developed, in collaboration with the selected applicants, an analysis workflow suitable both for the needs of the projects and for the computing infrastructure available to the applicants. All data, workflows, and deep learning models have been publicly released online following the FAIR principles. In particular, the data has been released on the BioImage Archive and the models on the BioImage ModelZoo. All workflows and documentation aiding reproducibility have been published on GitHub and archived on Zenodo.

In the following sections, we provide a summary of each project and links to its data, workflows, and models.

2.2.1 Projects of OC1

2.2.1.1 Treat CKD (project ID 3)

The project developed a robust image analysis pipeline to quantify fibrotic remodelling in heart and kidney tissues from rodent models of chronic kidney

disease. Focusing on Sirius Red–stained histological sections, where collagen–rich regions exhibit a strong red signal, the workflow uses Fiji’s Labkit to train a Random Forest pixel classifier distinguishing collagen, tissue, cells, and background. Pre–processing includes illumination normalisation and tissue masking to exclude vessels and borders. Quantification of collagen area relative to total tissue is fully automated. A Jupyter–based QC module allows optional manual refinement using SAM–enhanced masks, enabling reproducible, high–throughput fibrotic analysis across experimental replicates.

All details about this project, including how to install the required software and conduct the analysis pipeline that we developed in collaboration with the OC Applicants, can be found on the [AI4Life Website](#) and [GitHub](#). The FAIR data for this project is accessible via this [IDR data record](#).

2.2.1.2 Murine skeletal muscle analysis (project ID 6)

The project developed a complete pipeline for segmenting and tracking muscle fibre profiles across serial histological sections of murine skeletal muscle. Starting with spatial registration using BigWarp in Fiji, the pipeline aligns adjacent slices to compensate for morphological variation between sections. It then segments individual muscle fibres using Cellpose, a deep–learning model adapted to the dataset. To maintain fibre identity across sections, the pipeline integrates TrackMate for object linking, resulting in tracks that preserve fibre correspondence across the tissue volume. This enables detailed morphometric analysis of muscle architecture and supports quantitative studies of muscle structure in health and disease.

All details about this project, including how to install the required software and conduct the analysis pipeline that we developed in collaboration with the OC Applicants, can be found on the [AI4Life Website](#) and [GitHub](#). The FAIR data for this project is accessible via this [IDR data record](#).

2.2.1.3 Image–guided gating strategy for image–enabled cell sorting of phytoplankton (project ID 10)

The project developed an image–guided gating strategy specifically designed for image–enabled flow cytometry of phytoplankton. In flow cytometry, gating refers to drawing boundaries in feature space to separate and select specific cell populations from a mixed sample. Traditionally, these gates are based only on cytometry measurements such as

fluorescence intensity or scatter. In this project, however, the gating is guided by image-derived features, such as cell morphology and texture, extracted from fluorescence images of the phytoplankton. This provides richer information and allows for more accurate discrimination between species. The workflow automatically transforms raw FCS data into Logicle scale for better dynamic range handling, then computes Fisher Discriminant Ratios (FDR) across all channel pairs to identify which two-channel combinations best separate target phytoplankton species using precision-based ranking. Finally, it constructs device-compatible polygon gates—derived from cosine similarity thresholds and convex-hull extraction—that can be directly imported into the cytometer software. This enables fully automated, reproducible gating using only channels permitted by the instrument's constraints (maximum two channels per gate and up to fourteen gates).

All details about this project, including how to install the required software and conduct the analysis pipeline that we developed in collaboration with the OC Applicants, can be found on the [AI4Life Website](#) and [GitHub](#). The FAIR data for this project is accessible via this [Zenodo data record](#).

2.2.1.4 Segmentation and tracking of epithelial cells (project ID 11)

The project developed a modular pipeline to segment and track epithelial cell nuclei in time-lapse fluorescence microscopy datasets, focusing on live imaging of dynamic epithelial monolayers. Using the N2V (Noise2Void) framework, it first denoises images while preserving temporal integrity. Then, nuclei are segmented with a customised Cellpose model trained on domain-specific annotations. These masks are linked across frames using the Linear Assignment Problem tracker in Fiji's TrackMate, yielding lineage-resolved single-cell tracks. The final outputs include labelled tracks and quantification tables suitable for downstream dynamic phenotype analysis.

All details about this project, including how to install the required software and conduct the analysis pipeline that we developed in collaboration with the OC Applicants, can be found on the [AI4Life Website](#) and [GitHub](#). The FAIR data for this project is accessible via this [IDR data record](#).

2.2.1.5 Automated detection and quantification of senescent cells (project ID 47)

The project developed a semi-automated workflow to identify and quantify senescent cells in embryonic mouse neural tube tissue imaged by confocal microscopy. Initially, nuclei are segmented using

Cellpose on 2D slices, then senescent cell bodies are identified using a trained Labkit pixel classifier. The pipeline excludes cell extensions that may lead to oversegmentation. Subsequently, a 3D classifier refines the cell body volume across z-stacks, mapping each senescent body back to a nucleus. Output includes volumetric masks, per-cell fluorescence intensity profiles, and CSV quantification tables across multiple biological replicates.

All details about this project, including how to install the required software and conduct the analysis pipeline we developed in collaboration with the OC Applicants, can be found on the [AI4Life Website](#) and [GitHub](#).

2.2.1.6 *Atlas of Symbiotic partnerships in plankton (project ID 52)*

The project developed a lightweight, annotation-efficient segmentation workflow for identifying key organelles in FIB-SEM image volumes of microalgae engaged in symbiosis. The method integrates SAM (Segment Anything Model) to propose dense object masks from a single reference slice, followed by training a Random Forest classifier within napari using sparse scribbles on top of SAM embeddings. This allows efficient segmentation of chloroplasts, nuclei, and other structures without requiring large ground truth datasets. Results are provided as labelled image volumes suitable for 3D visualisation and morphometric analysis.

All details about this project, including how to install the required software and conduct the analysis pipeline that we developed in collaboration with the OC Applicants, can be found on the [AI4Life Website](#) and [GitHub](#). The FAIR data for this project is accessible via this [IDR data record](#).

Note that the workflow developed for this project and the resulting analysis contributed to two scientific publications: [Rao et al \(2025\)](#) and [Seifi et al \(2025\)](#).

2.2.1.7 *Automated and integrated cilia profiling (project ID 66)*

The project developed a high-content analysis pipeline to segment and quantify motile cilia in microscopy images of cultured cells expressing different kinesin motor proteins. It segments cilia using Labkit with a focus on thin, elongated morphology, while nuclei and expressing cells are segmented using Cellpose models. The pipeline links each detected cilium to its corresponding cell and computes geometrical descriptors

such as arc length, skeleton path, and best-fit ellipse. Additionally, it quantifies the signal intensity of perinuclear kinesin family (KIF) motor proteins using expanded nucleus masks, enabling correlation between expression and morphological phenotype.

All details about this project, including how to install the required software and conduct the analysis pipeline that we developed in collaboration with the OC Applicants, can be found on the [AI4Life Website](#) and [GitHub](#). The FAIR data for this project is accessible via this [IDR data record](#).

2.2.1.8 Leaf tracker plant species proof (project ID 74)

The project developed a deep learning-based pipeline for instance segmentation and time-resolved tracking of plant leaves in RGB images across developmental stages. A Detectron2 model fine-tuned on the PhenoBench dataset detects individual leaves in each frame. These are tracked over time using LapTrack, yielding identity-preserved trajectories that capture dynamic leaf emergence, growth, and senescence. A dedicated labelling interface allows efficient curation and re-training. This enables large-scale, longitudinal phenotyping studies of rosette architecture in controlled growth conditions.

All details about this project, including how to install the required software and conduct the analysis pipeline that we developed in collaboration with the OC Applicants, can be found on the [AI4Life Website](#) and [GitHub](#). The FAIR data for this project is accessible via this [IDR data record](#).

2.2.2 Projects of OC2

2.2.2.1 Automated species annotation in turbid waters (project ID 11)

The project's aim was to create an automated image-annotation pipeline to monitor the ecological status of vulnerable marine habitats according to the goals of multiple European Directives. The variability of the image quality and the diversity of the species made this project challenging.

Training a semantic segmentation model was not possible because they did not have enough ground-truth masks. However, they had a good amount of point annotations, which we could use as the prompt for the SAM2 model. We provided a pipeline for applicants to utilise their point prompts to produce

instance segmentation masks automatically, and then export the selected masks into COCO format, which was compatible with the BIIGLE that they are using as their main image and annotations platform.

All details about this project, including how to install the required software and conduct the analysis pipeline that we developed in collaboration with the OC Applicants, can be found on [GitHub](#). The FAIR data for this project is accessible via this [IDR data record](#).

2.2.2.2 *Optimizing calcium image acquisition with machine learning denoising algorithms (project ID 13)*

The project developed a deep-learning-powered pipeline to denoise calcium imaging data acquired from in vivo brain recordings. Leveraging U-Net-based models and temporal-aware filtering, the pipeline enhances weak calcium signals in fast imaging sessions while preserving true biological activity patterns. Integrated with Napari for visual QC and implemented in Jupyter notebooks, the method improves signal-to-noise ratio, aiding downstream spike inference and activity quantification.

All details about this project, including how to install the required software and conduct the analysis pipeline that we developed in collaboration with the OC Applicants, can be found on [GitHub](#). The FAIR data for this project is accessible via this [Zenodo data record](#).

2.2.2.3 *Diatom symbioses at planetary scale (project ID 14)*

The project developed a scalable image analysis pipeline for quantifying diatom-bacteria symbiotic interactions using large-scale plankton imaging datasets. Using a combination of classical segmentation (watershed, thresholding) and machine learning (pixel classifiers), the workflow identifies diatom frustules and co-localised symbiotic bacteria across diverse oceanic sampling stations. Geographic metadata is integrated to map symbiosis patterns globally. Outputs include co-occurrence statistics and spatial distribution overlays.

All details about this project, including how to install the required software and conduct the analysis pipeline that we developed in collaboration with the OC Applicants, can be found on [GitHub](#).

2.2.2.4 Automated segmentation of actin filaments in intact cells (EM) (project ID 21)

The project developed an electron microscopy image analysis pipeline focused on dense filamentous actin (F-actin) segmentation in whole-cell tomograms. It integrates pre-trained deep neural networks fine-tuned with human-annotated micrographs and applies post-processing to resolve filament bundling and branching points. The pipeline generates 3D reconstructions of cytoskeletal organisation, aiding studies on actin-mediated cell mechanics. Outputs include annotated segmentations, filament orientation metrics, and filament length distributions.

All details about this project, including how to install the required software and conduct the analysis pipeline we developed in collaboration with the OC Applicants, can be found on [GitHub](#).

2.2.2.5 Enhancing the effective resolution of intravital microscopy with digital expansion microscopy (project ID 23)

The project developed a deep learning pipeline to enhance in vivo two-photon microscopy images to super-resolved quality equivalent to 4× physical expansion microscopy, overcoming diffraction limits without the need for physical sample enlargement. By creating a synthetic training dataset from expansion microscopy images paired with simulated low-resolution counterparts, the model learned to recover fine subcellular features such as tumour microtubules and membrane protrusions in glioblastoma xenograft models expressing membrane-targeted GFP. Importantly, the pipeline integrates uncertainty estimation methods like variational autoencoders, supporting more reliable biological interpretation and downstream analysis.

All details about this project, including how to install the required software and conduct the analysis pipeline that we developed in collaboration with the OC Applicants, can be found on [GitHub](#). The FAIR data for this project is accessible via this [IDR data record](#).

2.2.2.6 Ultrastructural protein mapping through Correlation of Light and Electron Microscopy (project ID 26)

The project developed a correlative light and electron microscopy (CLEM) workflow for ultrastructural mapping of protein distributions in cells. It aligns high-resolution TEM images with fluorescence microscopy channels using fiducial markers, then overlays segmented protein signals onto electron-dense structures. Registration is automated through landmark-based matching in the *Napari* plugins. Quantitative readouts include protein localisation maps, proximity to organelles, and relative fluorescence intensities.

All details about this project, including how to install the required software and conduct the analysis pipeline that we developed in collaboration with the OC Applicants, can be found on [GitHub](#). The FAIR data for this project is accessible via this [IDR data record](#).

2.2.2.7 NeuroScan - A 3D human motor neuron disease platform for high-throughput drug screening (project ID 38)

The project developed a scalable 3D screening platform for analysing human motor neuron disease (MND) models using high-content microscopy. It segments neuron soma and neurite networks in 3D culture systems using hybrid models combining Cellpose and volumetric U-Nets. The workflow quantifies neurite outgrowth, soma size, and disease markers across drug-treated samples. Outputs support phenotype-based screening and therapeutic profiling in patient-derived iPSC models.

All details about this project, including how to install the required software and conduct the analysis pipeline that we developed in collaboration with the OC Applicants, can be found on [GitHub](#). The FAIR data for this project is accessible via this [IDR data record](#).

2.2.3 Projects of OC3

2.2.3.1 Improving nuclei segmentation using Cellprofiler and StarDist (project ID 3)

A group of researchers in Germany is using the Cell Painting assay to image different cellular structures with multiplexed dyes to understand which of them are affected by the compound. The automated

image acquisition and computational feature extraction generate rich, quantitative fingerprints of each compound's effect on cell morphology and subcellular organization.

The objective is to create an open database of the compounds with their phenotypic profile, also publishing the acquired images in the Bioimage Archive. This comprehensive dataset has the potential to help researchers across the world cluster compounds by mode of action, predict biological targets, and discover novel drug leads.

The automatic image-analysis workflow is implemented in CellProfiler. Because HepG2 cells are small and often form dense clusters, accurate segmentation can be challenging and typically requires specialized deep learning models, such as StarDist, to reliably delineate individual cells. To integrate StarDist and other [Biolm.io](https://biolm.io) - compatible networks into our pipeline, we have enhanced deeplmagej to run directly within CellProfiler, ensuring seamless execution of advanced segmentation and feature-extraction routines.

All details about this project, including how to install the required software and conduct the analysis pipeline that we developed in collaboration with the OC Applicants, can be found on [GitHub](https://github.com). The FAIR data for this project will be available soon.

2.2.3.2 3D Matrix Motility Map (3DM³) (project ID 11)

This project focuses on live-cell imaging of breast tumour spheroids embedded in collagen to analyze cancer cell migration, shape, and interaction with ECM architecture. This project aims to analyze cancer cell dissemination in 3D matrices, which is driven by interactions between cells and the extracellular matrix (ECM), particularly collagen.

The dataset includes 5D live imaging (X, Y, Z, T, C) acquired using widefield and confocal microscopy.

All details about this project, including how to install the required software and conduct the analysis pipeline that we developed in collaboration with the OC Applicants, can be found on [GitHub](https://github.com). The FAIR data for this project will be available soon.

2.2.3.3 The speed of life in trees (project ID 14)

The goal of this study was to automatically measure the fractional areas of vessels, axial and ray parenchyma, and fibers across the entire image, utilising a semantic segmentation pipeline.

Handling huge whole-slide images for 51 tree species and a lack of ground-truth masks for three (of four) cell types made this project challenging.

As a solution, we utilized FeatureForest ([Seifi et al \(2025\)](#)), a tool that was born and developed for a project "Atlas of Symbiotic partnerships in plankton" (project ID 52) of the first open call. With FeatureForest, we could train a model to generate very accurate masks for every cell. Later, the user will be able to assign labels to masks based on cell type. For the vessel cell type, for which we had ground-truth, we trained a deep-learning model combining several species data to be able to predict vessel masks across species.

All details about this project, including how to install the required software and conduct the analysis pipeline that we developed in collaboration with the OC Applicants, can be found on [GitHub](#). The FAIR data for this project will be available soon.

2.2.3.4 Imprints of Wind Disturbances on Wood Anatomy (project ID 17)

Disturbances play a crucial role in forest dynamics. The goal of this project was to analyse differences in wood quality among trees experiencing varying degrees of release (from none to the most intense). The desired outcome was the values of cell lumen area and cell wall thickness for each analysed cell (thousands of cells).

All details about this project, including how to install the required software and conduct the analysis pipeline that we developed in collaboration with the OC Applicants, can be found on [GitHub](#). The FAIR data for this project will be available soon.

2.2.3.5 Detection of Nuclear Pore Complexes with shape variability imaged by DNA PAINT (project ID 18)

The project's aim was to identify nuclear pore complexes in DNA-PAINT images, including those that deviate from the canonical structure in terms of diameter, stoichiometry, and circularity.

All details about this project, including how to install the required software and conduct the analysis pipeline that we developed in collaboration with the OC Applicants, can be found on [GitHub](#). The FAIR data for this project will be available soon.

2.2.3.6 Segmentation of sparse bacteria in human tissue (project ID 19)

The project's goal was to segment and analyse bacteria clusters in human biopsies and characterise the biological microenvironment of niches (intra/extracellular, cell type, cluster size).

The tissue samples are very large ($\sim 2 \text{ mm}^2 \times 60 \mu\text{m}$), bacteria are sparse, and hollow spheres approximately $1 \mu\text{m}$ in diameter; this makes the instance segmentation of bacteria a challenging task.

The provided solution includes training a 3D StarDist model to process 3D microscopy images of tissue.

All details about this project, including how to install the required software and conduct the analysis pipeline that we developed in collaboration with the OC Applicants, can be found on the AI4Life Website and [GitHub](#). The FAIR data for this project will be available soon.

2.2.3.7 Automatic microtubule doublet picking in tomograms (project ID 26)

The project's aim was to automatically detect and pick doublets with the correct polarity (i.e., all pointing the same) in Cryo-EM tomograms of cilia. Besides the full manual work, another challenge was that the existing software failed to assign polarity correctly.

The raw tilt series was gain and motion corrected using the Warp package. Tomogram alignment and reconstruction were performed using the EMAN2 package. All tomograms were reconstructed using the weighted back projection method and binned by four. For particle picking, the path of each doublet in the bin4 tomograms was modeled in EMAN2. Each doublet was traced by a separate contour made up of ~ 5 points, which were placed in the center of the filament using the different cross-views of the tomogram. Particles were extracted from the models with a box size enough to encompass the 8 nm repetitive structure present in the filaments and with an overlap between particles of 80%. In order to increase the particle count. Using the orientations traced by the model and the particles extracted, an initial 3D density map of the doublets was generated by averaging all the particles.

All details about this project, including how to install the required software and conduct the analysis pipeline that we developed in collaboration with the OC Applicants, can be found on [GitHub](#). The FAIR data for this project will be available soon.

3. Conclusion

Over the three-year lifetime of AI4Life, the Open Calls evolved from an exploratory idea into a mature, community-oriented support mechanism that has directly assisted 22 life-science projects and, indirectly, entire research communities that will benefit from the resulting workflows, models, and training material.

Starting from a simple call for proposals in OC1 (72 submissions, 8 retained), we progressively refined our process: we improved the application process and introduced one-to-one pre-selection consultations in OC2 (51 submissions, 7 retained) and further tightened the reviewing process and feasibility assessment in OC3 (28 submissions, 7 retained).

Each iteration produced better quality applications, better quality shared data, clearer formulated biological questions, more realistic expectations on both sides, and, we believe, clearer final decisions. The final selection process, consisting of an eligibility screen, anonymous reviewing, expert consultation, joint feasibility check, and weighted scoring, now serves as a reusable template for future similar initiatives.

Overall, the OC projects covered a wide range of microscopy methods, biological questions, and analysis challenges, highlighting the need for image analysis support across various scientific communities. It also illustrated the usefulness of many existing open-source tools used in the workflows developed by the AI4Life experts, as well as the need to innovate further in key analysis areas. The addition of the consultation phase helped applicants move forward with their projects, even in the case of final rejections. Finally, direct feedback provided by the users confirmed the usefulness and positive impact of the AI4Life OC.

The projects we supported span sub-cellular segmentation in electron microscopy to whole-organ phenotyping in light-sheet data, demonstrating that deep-learning solutions are applicable across scales when (i) the biological question is well defined, (ii) the imaging protocol is consistent, and (iii) the ground-truth annotation effort is accepted as a shared investment. Trained networks, example datasets, and Jupyter-based training notebooks have been publicly released and deposited in the BiImage Archive, EMPIAR, the BiImage Model Zoo, Github, and Zenodo under permissive licences, aligning with AI4Life's FAIR and EOSC-ready mandate. Furthermore, the impact of the OCs has already materialized in two peer-reviewed publications, and several others are currently being written.

Consequently, the AI4Life Open Calls have not only delivered on Objective 4 ("Organise open calls and challenges") but have also become a flagship instrument for Objectives 1,

2, 5, and 6: they populated the service landscape with ready-to-use AI tools, enriched the BioImage Archive Model Zoo with high-quality reference datasets, and the BioImage Model Zoo with high-performing models, thus empowering core platforms such as ilastik, CellPose, and DeepImageJ with plug-and-play models.

